

VENDOR MANAGEMENT INVENTORY FOR ENHANCED SUPPLY CHAIN PERFORMANCE METRICS OF SELECTED MANUFACTURING COMPANIES

John Paulo R. Quiton, Ena A. Bernal, Ph.D.

*Graduate School, Colegio de San Juan de Letran Calamba,
Calamba, Laguna, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11115592>

ABSTRACT

This research investigated the impact of Vendor Management Inventory (VMI) implementation on supply chain efficiency, customer satisfaction, fill rate, and cost savings in selected manufacturing companies in Luzon. It aimed to identify the current state of supply chain performance, challenges in VMI implementation, top priorities of these companies, and strategies to improve VMI's supply chain performance. The study utilized a descriptive research design and quantitative methods to comprehensively understand VMI processes and inventory control. Findings reveal that VMI positively influences logistics cost-to-sales ratios and order fill rates. While the selected companies outperform industry averages, they acknowledge challenges like delayed shipping. The survey also uncovered insights related to data sharing and distributor relationships. The strategic priorities of the companies vary, emphasizing cost efficiency, customer satisfaction, and technology integration. To enhance supply chain performance, a comprehensive framework was developed, encompassing phases like assessment, strategy development, implementation, monitoring, and adaptation. This research underscored the importance of efficient supply chain management and agile VMI practices in adapting to dynamic market conditions and ensuring long-term competitiveness.

Keywords: *Supply Chain, VMI, Vendor Management Inventory*

INTRODUCTION

Effective VMI is crucial in the manufacturing sector, ensuring smooth operations, optimized inventory levels, and strong supplier relationships for distributors. VMI fosters collaboration between manufacturers and distributors, facilitating real-time data sharing to streamline the flow of goods. It aims to ensure the right products are available when needed,

enhancing overall supply chain performance. Companies implementing VMI experience benefits such as improved demand forecasting, enhanced supply chain visibility, streamlined replenishment processes, and reduced stockouts. In Luzon's manufacturing sector, VMI optimizes supply chains, aligns production schedules with supplier capabilities, reduces disruptions, controls inventory costs, and enables adaptability to market dynamics, ultimately improving cost-effectiveness, fill rate, and customer satisfaction (Rahul & Essex, 2011).

Research Questions

The primary question of the research is how does the implementation of VMI impact supply chain efficiency, customer satisfaction, fill rate and cost savings in the context of the selected manufacturing companies in Luzon?

This study aimed to:

1. Identify current Supply Chain Performance vis-à-vis the current status of VMI System in the selected manufacturing companies in terms of:
 - i. Fill rate
 - ii. Cost
 - iii. Customer Satisfaction
2. Determine the challenges encountered on VMI System by the selected manufacturing companies in terms of:
 - i. Relationship
 - ii. Data sharing
3. Identify the top three priorities of the selected manufacturing companies on VMI.
4. Develop strategies to improve the Supply Chain Performance of the VMI System in the selected manufacturing companies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research adopted a descriptive study approach, utilizing quantitative methods to gain insights into VMI processes and inventory control within the manufacturing and distribution sectors. Descriptive research aimed to accurately depict the characteristics and current state of the phenomenon under investigation, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of VMI practices. Through surveys and statistical analysis, quantitative data were collected and presented, allowing for a detailed examination of VMI practices and their impact on supply chain operations (Vijayamohan, 2022).

Research Locale

Data for the study were collected from well-known manufacturers in the Philippines, chosen for their multinational status and dedicated supply chain departments, ensuring robust customer service management. These companies heavily import goods and raw materials for production and are known practitioners of VMI within Luzon. Specifically, the study focuses on manufacturers of instant noodles, milk, and home cleaning products. Data collection involved engaging representatives from each company's customer service division, despite challenges posed by data privacy restrictions in the research locale.

Population and Sampling Design

The manufacturing companies that were chosen for the study are represented by the respondents. They are the ones who are knowledgeable enough to respond to the study's questions. The organization to which the researcher belonged was where the study first began. In order to broadly compare the study, the researcher looked for other well-known businesses in the Philippines that produced well-known goods, just like the organization of the researcher.

Research Instrument

This section details the methodologies employed for data collection in the research study, ensuring the reliability and validity of the findings. A structured questionnaire with Likert scale responses was used to gather quantitative data on respondents' perceptions regarding current supply chain performance, VMI system status, encountered challenges, and priorities. Interviews were conducted via Zoom after obtaining respondents' confirmation. Additionally, the researcher's firsthand observations of supply chain processes provided contextual insights. To validate data, a supply chain professional with extensive expertise reviewed the questionnaire for correctness and reliability. The

research targets specific industry benchmarks, including order fill rate, cost targets, and customer service levels, aiming for optimal performance within defined ranges.

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter requesting study participation was drafted, and a questionnaire designed by the researcher, validated by the advisor and a procurement professional, was distributed via email. The questionnaire, crafted based on pertinent research, aimed to gather comprehensive data. Research was conducted across three selected industrial firms in Luzon, with surveys and interviews conducted online due to geographical constraints, utilizing social media platforms for communication.

Management and Treatment of Data

This study employs known data gathering techniques and statistical analysis to achieve this goal in manufacturing companies. Initially, a self-administered questionnaire gauges the company's current VMI system. Engagement levels with VMI are determined based on questionnaire responses, assigning scores accordingly. The study utilizes straightforward measurement data, with Microsoft Excel facilitating result generation through calculations and graphical representations, aiding the researcher in analyzing gathered data effectively.

RESULTS

Performance	Target (lowest acceptable)	Noodles Product Company	Milk Products Company	Health Care Products Company
Cost to Sales Ratio	7%	5%	6%	5%
Order Fill Rate	85%	90-100%	90-100%	90-100%
Customer Service Satisfaction	85%	90-100%	90-100%	90-100%

Table 1. Summary of Supply Chain Performance of the Selected Companies

Summary	Yes	No	Not Sure
Cost	54%	28%	19%
Order Fill Rate	50%	44%	6%
Customer Satisfaction	65%	33%	2%

Table 2. Summary of Status of Vendor Management Inventory of the Selected Companies

Summary of Challenges		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Relationship	Lack of Trust and Collaboration	26%	41%	33%	0	0
	Lack of Flexibility and Adaptability	33%	22%	19%	26%	0%
	Slow Conflict Resolution	0%	70%	30%	0%	0%
Data Sharing	Issues on Data Sharing and Communication	11%	59%	15%	15%	0
	Not Responsible and Accountable	70%	22%	7%	0	0

Table 3. Summary of the Challenges Encountered by the Selected Companies

Items	Noodle Products Company	Milk Products Company	Health Care Products Company
Reduced Cost	6	5	4
Order fill rate	5	4	3
Customer Satisfaction	4	6	6
Risk Management	3	2	5
Collaboration	2	3	2
Data Sharing	1	1	1

Table 4. Summary of the Priorities of the Selected Companies

VMI System	Aspects	Strategies
Cost to Sales Ratio	Inventory Discrepancy No Optimal Inventory Level	Cost to Sales Ratio Optimization
		Conduct a thorough review of existing cost control measures within the VMI system.
		Identify opportunities for efficiency improvement without compromising product availability.
		Dynamic Inventory Management
		Implement dynamic inventory management strategies for real-time adjustments based on demand fluctuations.
		Collaborate closely with distributors and retailers to align inventory levels with customer demand patterns.
Order Fill Rate	Fluctuation of Orders Monitoring Other Categories with Low Order Fill Rate Demand Focused Cycle Time Based on Order Quantity	Order Fill Rate Optimization: Predictive Analytics for Demand Forecasting
		Integrate predictive analytics into the VMI system to enhance demand forecasting accuracy.
		Utilize historical data and market insights to optimize order fill rates and minimize stockouts.
Customer Satisfaction	Instances of Incorrect Shipment	VMI-Integrated Customer Feedback Mechanism:
		Integrate VMI data with customer feedback mechanisms to identify areas for improvement.
		Leverage VMI insights to enhance customer satisfaction by ensuring product availability and timely deliveries.
Lack of Flexibility and Adaptability	Potential Changes in the Market Handling of Seasonal Demand	Market Change Adaptation
		Continuous Monitoring and Analysis
		Establish a dedicated team for ongoing market analysis, identifying trends, and assessing potential disruptions.
		Implement proactive strategies to adapt the VMI system to changing market conditions.
		Agile Supply Chain Design
		Design the VMI system with flexibility and scalability to accommodate variations in demand and market preferences.
		Regularly review and update the system to align with evolving market dynamics.
Issues on Data Sharing and Communication	Not Sharing of Data on time Late Sending of Inventory Report	Communication Excellence:
		Diversified Communication Channels:
		Expand communication channels beyond Viber to ensure efficiency and reliability.
		Implement a multichannel approach, including email, dedicated software, and regular meetings for effective collaboration.
		Communication Training and Protocols:
		Provide communication training programs to improve skills and streamline information flow.
		Establish communication protocols to ensure clarity, responsiveness, and accountability among stakeholders.

Table 5. Strategies Developed to Improve Supply Chain Performance

DISCUSSION

The table 1 indicates that the selected companies maintain favorable cost-to-sales ratios, with Noodle Products and Health Care Products sustaining a 5% ratio, showcasing effective control over operational expenses. Despite a slightly higher ratio of 6% for Milk Product Company, it remains competitive in the dairy and food industry. These ratios highlight the companies' commitment to efficient supply chain management amid evolving market dynamics. Additionally, their impressive order fill rates and high customer service satisfaction, consistently ranging from 90% to 100%, exceed the industry average of 85%, emphasizing their excellence in supply chain management and customer service. However, it's important to note that these exceptional scores don't imply perfection (Johnson, n.d.).

Representatives from selected companies in table 2 show a strong focus on cost management within VMI, as reflected in their good scores in the "cost" category. This underscores their awareness of the importance of cost control and efficiency in VMI implementation. Despite challenges such as delayed shipping and rising raw material prices, the supply chain has remained resilient, ensuring consistent product availability and high order fill rates. Efficient inventory management not only optimizes supply chain operations but also enhances customer satisfaction and loyalty. Companies demonstrate readiness to address stockouts promptly, highlighting their commitment to delivering an exceptional customer experience.

The survey revealed in table 3 that the selected companies face challenges in data sharing, particularly regarding the accuracy and timeliness of inventory reports. While most respondents agree on the importance of data sharing, there's a need to ensure precision and punctuality in inventory information. Conflict resolution appears less problematic, with a notable neutral stance from 30% of respondents. However, timely conflict resolution remains vital for efficient VMI and supply chain operations. Additionally, issues related to flexibility and adaptability in a changing market are acknowledged by 26% of respondents, highlighting the need for a more agile approach to VMI. Lastly, while trust and collaboration with distributors are generally strong, there's room for improvement to foster stronger partnerships in VMI.

In table 4, the Noodle Product Company emphasizes cost reduction, high order fill rates, and customer satisfaction to deliver quality products while managing costs effectively. The Milk Product Company prioritizes customer service satisfaction, cost reduction, and maintaining a high order fill rate to thrive in the dairy and food industry. In the healthcare sector, the Health Care Product Company focuses on risk management, quality standards, and research to ensure product safety and effectiveness. For companies implementing Vendor Managed Inventory (VMI), key priorities include cost efficiency,

customer satisfaction, and technology integration to optimize inventory levels, enhance customer loyalty, and drive efficient operations.

By implementing these strategies attached in table 5, the selected manufacturing companies can significantly improve their VMI system's supply chain performance, effectively address market changes, enhance communication, achieve higher order fill rates, improve customer satisfaction, and proactively manage supply chain risks. The focus on adaptability, collaboration, and data-driven decision-making will be instrumental in overcoming these challenges.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the analysis highlighted the robust performance of the selected manufacturing companies in terms of Cost to Sales Ratio, Order Fill Rate, and Customer Service Satisfaction within the framework of VMI. The companies demonstrate efficient cost management, surpassing industry standards in order fill rates and customer satisfaction. Despite challenges such as demand forecasting and communication issues, companies are leveraging VMI to drive cost savings and operational efficiencies. The companies' strategic priorities, including cost efficiency and customer satisfaction, align with industry best practices, ensuring competitiveness. To enhance supply chain performance, developed strategies emphasize optimizing cost-to-sales ratios, improving order fill rates through predictive analytics, enhancing customer satisfaction via social media engagement, and prioritizing data accuracy and communication. Overall, these strategies equip companies to navigate challenges, foster collaboration, and drive continuous improvement in their VMI systems.

Recommendations

The recommendation proposes a comprehensive research initiative aimed at optimizing the Vendor Managed Inventory (VMI) system while adhering to the Data Privacy Act. This involves reviewing existing cost control measures and exploring dynamic inventory management strategies to enhance operational efficiency while ensuring product availability, in compliance with data privacy regulations. Additionally, the integration of predictive analytics into the system is suggested to improve order fill rates and customer satisfaction through timely deliveries, while ensuring data security and privacy are maintained as per the Data Privacy Act.

Adaptation to market changes is highlighted, with a focus on establishing a dedicated research team to monitor trends and implement agile supply chain design principles, ensuring that data access is limited to authorized personnel as per the Data Privacy Act guidelines. Communication excellence is emphasized, suggesting the diversification of communication channels and the implementation of training programs to improve collaboration among stakeholders, while also ensuring that any communication involving sensitive data complies with the Data Privacy Act.

Opportunities for future research are identified, including broader industry and geographical scope, along with recommendations for enhancing survey methodologies

while ensuring that data collection and analysis processes are conducted in accordance with the principles outlined in the Data Privacy Act to protect the confidentiality and integrity of the company's data.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

While VMI offers several benefits to both manufacturers and distributors, there are ethical considerations that need to be taken into account. Here are some key ethical considerations for VMI in manufacturing and distribution:

Transparency and Information Sharing: VMI requires a high level of information sharing between the supplier and the customer. Ethical considerations arise regarding the extent and nature of information shared. Both parties must agree on what information is necessary for effective inventory management while respecting each other's confidentiality and privacy.

Data Security and Privacy: With increased information sharing, there is a risk of data breaches and unauthorized access to sensitive business information. Manufacturers and distributors must establish robust data security measures to protect confidential information and customer data. Implementing secure communication channels, encryption.

Trust and Collaboration: Successful VMI implementation requires a high level of trust and collaboration between manufacturers and distributors. Ethical considerations revolve around fostering a relationship built on mutual respect, open communication, and a shared understanding of goals and expectations. Manufacturers should avoid exploiting their position of power and prioritize long-term partnerships based on trust and fairness.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express his sincere gratitude and appreciation to the following individuals and entities who have played an invaluable role in the successful completion of this research.

First and foremost, the researcher extends his deepest thanks to Dr. Ena A. Bernal for her unwavering guidance, expertise, and invaluable insights as his adviser throughout this research journey. Her mentorship has been instrumental in shaping this study and his academic growth.

The researcher would like to acknowledge Dr. Heidi Maneclang, the OIC of the Graduate School, for her continuous support and encouragement. Your commitment to fostering a conducive research environment is truly commendable.

The researcher's heartfelt appreciation goes to the esteemed research panels: Dr. Romulo N. Ulibas, Dr. Marie Joy Q. Elomina, and Dr. Carmella N. Hemedez, for their

meticulous review, constructive feedback, and valuable recommendations that significantly enhanced the quality of this research.

The researcher is deeply grateful to the research respondents who willingly participated in this study. Your contributions were essential in gathering the necessary data and insights.

The researcher wishes to extend his gratitude to his ever-supportive manager, Carmelle Gupit, for understanding the demands of research and providing unwavering support throughout this endeavor.

The researcher wants to express his love and appreciation to his parents, Nani and Marie, for their endless encouragement, understanding, and belief in his academic pursuits. Their unwavering support has been his driving force.

Special thanks to his employer, Monde Nissin, for the financial support that made this educational journey possible. Your commitment to help is genuinely appreciated.

Last but certainly not least, the researcher acknowledges the almighty God for His guidance, wisdom, and strength throughout this research journey. His grace has been his constant source of inspiration and resilience.

This research would not have been possible without the collective support, guidance, and encouragement of all those mentioned above. Thank you for being a vital part of this academic endeavor.

REFERENCES

Awati, Rahul & Essex, David. (2011). What is vendor-managed inventory (VMI)?. <https://www.techtarget.com/searcherp/definition/vendor-managed-inventory-VMI>

Johnson, Bradley. (n.d.). Fill Rate Definition, Formula, and 2 Calculation Steps. <https://www.bluecart.com/blog/fill-rate-definition#:~:text=fill%20rate%20percentage%3F-A%20good%20fill%20rate%20percentage,close%20to%20100%25%20as%20possible.&text=The%20average%20company's%20fill%20rate,goals%20of%20any%20warehousing%20team>.

Vijayamohan, Parvathi. (2023). Descriptive Research 101: Definition, Methods and Examples. <https://surveysparrow.com/blog/descriptive-research-101-the-definitive-guide/>
